

Wood intensities in a 19th-century log house prior to and post-rehabilitation

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Background

Wood is a renewable resource, but not an unlimited one. Circular use of wood can mitigate greenhouse gas emissions and spare virgin resources. To plan for the circular use of building materials, it is important to study the availability of building materials in the built environment and the materials liberated during renovation. There exist multiple studies on so-called material intensities in buildings (Amini et al., 2024; Arceo et al., 2021; Fishman et al., 2024; Nasiri et al., 2023), but few evaluate the material intensities before and after renovation. In this study, we try to fill the knowledge gap by performing a case study of a log house from the 19th century, upgraded to a student residence satisfying the building requirements for new Norwegian buildings.

Keywords: Building constructions, material Intensities, renovation, timber.

Experimental

The building is a pre-cut log house from 1899, located in the city centre of Trondheim, Norway (Figure 1). It has been renovated multiple times since it was first constructed, but not as comprehensively as the current renovation. During the last renovation, most of the foundation and the building shell were preserved, but all inner walls, slabs, and wall layers are new.

The construction site was visited 3 times during the renovation phase, and the construction was documented with photographs. Architectural drawings were used to calculate the material volume of the building elements, complemented by information from the contractor, photos, and literature on architectural building history. The dimensions of the structural elements that were not visible in the architectural drawings or in the

photos were estimated based on literature and the verbal information from the contractor. The beams carrying the slabs before renovation were counted from images that the contractor had taken before the beams were taken down, while the width of the flooring on top and below the beams was estimated to be 50 mm and 25 mm, respectively, based on historic engineering curriculum (Bugge, 1918).

The renovated building is a light timber frame structure with dimensions given in Table 1. The number and dimensions of all the building elements were used to calculate the total wood volume which was multiplied with an average wood density of 430 kg/m³.

Table 1. Building element dimensions

	Walls		Slabs		Roof	
Original building	Length of walls	114 m	Beams	72 x 192 mm	Load-bearing beams	130 x 130 mm
	Height of walls	7.5 m				
	Log width	70 mm			Flooring	50 mm and 25 mm
	Inside cladding width	12 mm	Roof planks	70 mm		
	Outside cladding width	40 mm				
	Sill plate	130 x 130 mm				
Area, windows and doors	120 m ²					
Renovated building	Studs	48 x 98 mm	Beams	72 x 192 mm	Load-bearing beams	130 x 130 mm
	Bracing	48 x 98 mm			Truss	72 x 192 mm
	Purlins and rafters	48 x 21 mm	Flooring (Particle board)	50 and 25 mm	Roof planks	70 mm

Results and Discussion

The wood intensity in the renovated building is lower than it was in the original building (Table 1). In the original building, all the inner walls were log walls, whereas the renovated building has insulated light timber frame walls. Hence, the renovated building is more material- and energy-efficient than the original building. However, the material intensity is still large in the renovated building since the outer log walls and roof are kept as they were.

Table 1. Wood intensities before and after renovations

	Original building	Renovated building
Wood Intensity [kg/m²]	228	203

According to the contractor, the cost of renovating this building was around three times as high as the cost of building a completely new building. This building is a special case because it is protected by law due to historical significance, which meant that the cladding and windows had to be specially designed and produced to fit the appearance of the original building. Even without protection, renovating buildings is expensive, meaning that building owners may have to demolish instead of renovate. One could also argue that older buildings have intrinsic cultural and architectural values that cannot be measured in monetary value. In this case, the protection of the building was what prompted the building owner to renovate it back to its original look, rather than demolishing it. However, protection could also lead to buildings deteriorating because the owners find it too expensive to renovate.

As foundation is mostly made from concrete, with more embodied GHG emissions than timber (Hegeir et al., 2022), renovating a building as opposed to demolishing it could help mitigate emissions. Renovating the building to fulfil the energy requirements for today will also help with energy reductions in the use phase, and make the building a more pleasant home to live in.

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